

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL
A summary of the systematic literature review

N	Authors	Country	Industry	SD	Sample (%F)	Measurement CP	Journal
1	Abdullah et al. (2017)	Pakistan	Casual sector	CS	322 (37%)	Self-Report	Sustainability
2	Abukhait et al. (2023)	United Arab Emirates	Hospitality	CS	252 (49.4%)	Supervisor-Report	Review of Managerial Science
3	Aleksic et al. (2016)	Slovenia	(1) Casual sector; (2) Manufacturing	CS	(1) 129 (59%); (2) 165 (34%)	Self-Report and Supervisor-Report	European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology
4	Al-Madadha et al. (2023)	Jordan	Telecommunication	CS	344 (55.9%)	Self-Report	Organizacija
5	Audenaert & Decramer (2018)	Belgium	Industrial	CS	213 (36%)	Self-Report	Journal of Management & Organization
6	Bhatti et al. (2022)	Malaysia	Information Technology	CS	227 (21.1%)	Self-Report	Przestrzen Spoleczna
7	Bouzari & Karatepe (2020)	Iran	Hospitality	L	187 (39.6%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism
8	Cai et al. (2022)	Pakistan	Education	CS	237 (43.5%)	Self-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
9	Chen et al. (2015)	Taiwan	Manufacturing	CS	337 (17%)	Self-Report	Creativity and Innovation Management
10	Cheung & Zhang (2021)	China	(1) Knowledge-Based; (2) Professional Services	CS	(1) 100 (52.4%); (2) 175 (63,7%)	Supervisor-Report	Asia Pacific Journal of Management
11	Chiang et al. (2022)	Taiwan	Education	L	341 (74.5%)	Self-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
12	Choi et al. (2021)	Korea	Manufacturing and Service	CS	439 (30.3%)	Self-Report	Sustainability
13	Christensen-Salem et al. (2021)	Taiwan	Public sector	L	795 (34%)	Supervisor-Report	The International Journal of Human Resource Management
14	Chuang et al. (2019)	Taiwan	Education	L	135 (81%)	Coworker-Report	Personnel Review
15	Darvishmotevali et al. (2018)	Cyprus	Hospitality	CS	283 (52%)	Self-Report	International Journal of Hospitality Management
16	De Stobbeleir et al. (2011)	Not reported	Consulting	CS	456 (56%)	Supervisor-Report	Academy of Management Journal
17	Eslamlou et al. (2021)	Not reported	Aviation	L	121 (60.3%)	Supervisor-Report	Sustainability
18	Gilmore et al. (2013)	China	Pharmaceutical	CS	212 (74%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Organizational Behavior
19	Glaser et al. (2015)	Germany	General population	CS	830 (34.8%)	Self-Report	Journal of Personnel Psychology
20	Gong & Zhang (2017)	China	Various industries	L	264 (49.2%)	Supervisor-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
21	Gupta & Singh (2014)	India	Public Research	CS	496 (25%)	Self-Report	The International Journal of Human Resource Management
22	He et al. (2018)	China	Various industries	CS	335 (15.2%)	Supervisor-Report	Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources
23	Herbst & Hausberg (2022)	Not reported	Not reported	CS	528 (-%)	Self-Report	International Journal of Innovation Management
24	Hon (2012)	China	Hospitality and Service	CS	219 (42%)	Self-Report	International Journal of Hospitality Management
25	Hon et al. (2014)	China	High-tech, Manufacturing and Service	CS	452 (47%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Management
26	Hora et al. (2021)	USA	Food manufacturing	L	335 (64%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Organizational Behavior

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27	Hu et al. (2019)	China	Casual sector	CS	275 (70.9%)	Self-Report	Journal of Management and Organization
28	Hu et al. (2022)	Pakistan	Manufacturing (with environmental certification)	CS	311 (34.7%)	Self-Report	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health
29	Hwang et al. (2023)	Korea	Manufacturing	CS	321 (50.2%)	Self-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
30	Ishaque et al. (2019)	Punjab	Education	CS	302 (-%)	Supervisor-Report	Amazonia Investiga
31	Kalyar & Kalyar (2018)	Pakistan	Service and Manufacturing	CS	753 (14.1%)	Self-Report	Personnel Review
32	Karatepe (2016)	Cameroon	Hospitality	CS	212 (48%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism
33	Karkouliau et al. (2023)	Lebanon	Banking	CS	301 (46%)	Self-Report	International Journal of Process Management and Benchmarking
34	Khan & Abbas (2022)	Pakistan	Service and Manufacturing	CS	303 (27.4%)	Self-Report	Thinking Skills and Creativity
35	Leung et al. (2014)	China	Education	CS	189 (45.5%)	Supervisor-Report	Asia Pacific Journal of Management
36	Li et al. (2020a)	Taiwan	Technology and Manufacturing	L	125 (46.4%)	Supervisor-Report	Personnel Review
37	Li et al. (2018)	China	Information Technology	CS	135 (46%)	Self-Report	Group & Organization Management
38	Li et al. (2020b)	China	High-tech	L	346 (27.7%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Creative Behavior
39	Li et al. (2021)	China	High-tech	CS	237 (39.7%)	Supervisor-Report	Social Behavior and Personality
40	Li et al. (2022)	China	Manufacturing	L	206 (20.4%)	Supervisor-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
41	Liu et al. (2022)	China	Retail	CS	206 (62.6%)	Supervisor-Report	Human Resource Management
42	Liu et al. (2019)	China	High-tech	L	318 (24%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Creative Behavior
43	Madjar et al. (2002)	Bulgaria	Apparel manufacturing	CS	265 (97%)	Supervisor-Report	Academy of Management Journal
44	Makhija & Akbar (2019)	Pakistan	Information Technology	CS	240 (17.5%)	Supervisor-Report	International Journal of Innovation
45	Malik et al. (2015)	Pakistan	Not reported	CS	181 (14%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Organizational Behavior
46	Man et al. (2020)	China	Medical	L	300 (78%)	Supervisor-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
47	Martinaityte et al. (2019)	Lithuania	Banking and cosmetics	CS	329 (96%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Management
48	Mohammed & Kamalanabhan (2019)	India	Information Technology	CS	401 (31.2%)	Self-Report	Vine Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems
49	Nwanzu & Babalola (2022)	Nigeria	Public & Private sectors	CS	148 (54.7%)	Self-Report	Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Science
50	Ozturk & Karatepe (2019)	Russia	Hospitality	L	159 (67.9%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management
51	Peng & Chen (2022)	Taiwan	Information Technology	CS	413 (75%)	Supervisor-Report	Current Psychology
52	Prince & Rao (2022)	India	Information Technology	CS	285 (71.2%)	Self-Report	Management and Organization Review
53	Putra et al. (2023)	Indonesia	Software Development	CS	253 (22%)	Self-Report	WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics
54	Qian & Jiang (2023)	China	Various industries	L	107 (54.2%)	Self-Report	Internet Resarch

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55	Ren et al. (2021)	China	Not reported	CS	387 (51.2%)	Supervisor-Report	Chinese Management Studies
56	Torner (2023)	Colombia	Electrical manufacturing	CS	448 (39.1%)	Self-Report	Revista Galega de Economía
57	Shaheen et al. (2020)	Pakistan	Banking	CS	303 (33%)	Supervisor-Report	Thinking Skills and Creativity
58	Shalley et al. (2009)	USA	Not reported	CS	1430 (51%)	Self-Report	Academy of Management Journal
59	Shaw & Choi (2023)	USA	Consulting	CS	170 (53.8%)	Supervisor-Report	Acta Psychologica
60	Simmons et al. (2014)	USA	Not reported	CS	128 (42%)	Supervisor-Report	Creativity Research Journal
61	Song et al. (2017)	China	Not reported	CS	752 (53.7%)	Self-Report	Journal of Managerial Psychology
62	Sumaneeva et al. (2021)	Russia	Hospitality	L	101 (65%)	Self-Report	Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism
63	Sun et al. (2020)	China	Not reported	CS	365 (57.4%)	Self-Report	Telematics and Informatics
64	Tang & Sun (2021)	China	Not reported	CS	186 (52.7%)	Supervisor-Report	Finance Research Letters
65	Thundiyil et al. (2016)	China	Chemical	CS	459 (46%)	Supervisor-Report	Chinese Management Studies
66	Tierney & Farmer (2002)	Not reported	(1) Consumer Goods; (2) High-tech	CS	(1) 502 (-%); (2) 104 (-%)	Supervisor-Report	Academy of Management Journal
67	Tierney & Farmer (2011)	Not reported	Not reported	L	145 (68.8%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Applied Psychology
68	Tonnessen et al. (2021)	Norway	Not reported	CS	237 (50%)	Self-Report	Technological Forecasting and Social Change
69	Villajos et al. (2019)	Spain	Varioues industries	L	209 (60.8%)	Self-Report	Sustainability
70	Wadei et al. (2021)	Ghana	Service industries	L	512 (38.7%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Creative Behavior
71	Wang et al. (2023)	China	Manufacturing, Finance and Internet	L	1384 (43.9%)	Supervisor-Report	Current Psychology
72	Xie et al. (2020)	China	Not reported	CS	386 (44.4%)	Supervisor-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
73	Yang et al. (2021)	China	Electronics	L	347 (33.1%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Business and Psychology
74	Yang et al. (2022)	China	Banking	L	368 (79.4%)	Supervisor-Report	Sustainability
75	Ye et al. (2014)	China	High-tech	CS	120 (36.7%)	Supervisor-Report	International Journal of Information Systems and Change Management
76	Yoon et al. (2015)	South Korea	Not reported	CS	241 (27%)	Coworker-Report	Social Behavior and Personality: An International Journal
77	Yulianti et al. (2022)	Indonesia	Education	CS	200 (61%)	Self-Report	Journal of Behavioral Science
78	Yulianti & Usman (2019)	Indonesia	Media	CS	154 (-%)	Self-Report	International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change
79	Zhang et al. (2017)	China	Industrial	CS	162 (41.4%)	Supervisor-Report	Frontiers in Psychology
80	Zhang & Zhao (2021)	China	Not reported	CS	288 (44.8%)	Self-Report	Chinese Management Studies
81	Zhang & Bartol (2010)	China	Not reported	CS	367 (34.8%)	Supervisor-Report	Journal of Applied Psychology
82	Zheng et al. (2022)	China	Not reported	L	292 (47.3%)	Supervisor-Report	Leadership & Organization Development Journal

Note: Study Design (SD): longitudinal (L) or cross-sectional (CS). Creative Performance (CP).